

Vertex-edge Domination of Tensor product graphs

A. D. Akwu^{1*}, A. I. Nyianshima¹

¹ Department of Mathematics, University of Agriculture,
Makurdi, Nigeria.

*Orchid iD:0000-0002-4665-5040

Received: 12 Sep 2020

Accepted: 23 Dec 2020

Published Online: 31 Dec 2020

Abstract: A vertex v of a graph $G = (V, E)$ is said to vertex-edge dominate every edge incident to v as well as every edge adjacent to these incident edges. A set $D \subset V$ is a vertex-edge dominating set if every edge of E is vertex-edge dominated by at least one vertex of D . The minimum cardinality of a vertex-edge dominating set of G is the vertex-edge domination number denoted as $\gamma_{ve}(G)$. In this paper, we give the vertex-edge domination number of tensor product graphs.

Key words: Vertex-edge domination number, Tensor product graphs

1. Introduction

Let $G = G(V, E)$ be a simple connected graph. The length of the shortest $x-y$ path in G is the distance between x and y denoted by $d(x, y)$ and $\max\{d(x, y) : x, y \in V(G)\}$ is the diameter of G denoted by $\text{diam}(G)$. The path on n vertices is denoted by P_n and a cycle on n vertices is denoted by C_n . A complete graph, bipartite graph and bipartite graph minus a one-factor is denoted by $K_n, K_{n,n}, K_{n,n} - I$ respectively.

For two graphs G and H , their tensor product $G \times H$ has vertex set $V(G) \times V(H)$ in which two vertices (g_1, h_1) and (g_2, h_2) are adjacent whenever $g_1g_2 \in E(G)$ and $h_1h_2 \in E(H)$.

A subset $D \subset V(G)$ is a dominating set, abbreviated DS of a graph G if every vertex of $V(G) \setminus D$ has a neighbor in D . The domination number of a graph G denoted by $\gamma(G)$, is the dominating set of G with minimum cardinality, see [3]. A vertex $v \in V(G)$ dominates an edge $e \in E(G)$ if v is incident with e or with an edge adjacent to e . The vertex-edge dominating set of G was introduced in [9] as the subset $D \subset V(G)$ if every edge of G is vertex-edge dominated by a vertex in D . The vertex-edge domination number of a graph G is the minimum cardinality of a vertex-edge dominating set of G and it is denoted by $\gamma_{ve}(G)$. Vertex-edge domination of cubic graphs was given in [12]. Also, independent vertex-edge domination and external vertex-edge domination were discussed in [2] and [11] respectively. An updated survey on distance-based domination parameters in graphs can be found in [10]. Further studies of vertex-edge domination in graphs can be found in [1, 4–8, 13].

Little or non have been done on vertex-edge domination of tensor product graphs. The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In next section, we give the vertex-edge domination number of tensor product graphs $P_m \times P_n$, $C_m \times P_n$ and $C_m \times C_n$. In section 3, vertex-edge domination number of tensor product graphs $P_m \times K_n$, $C_m \times K_n$, $K_m \times K_n$ and $G \times K_n$ for any connected graph G were given.

2. Vertex-edge domination number of $P_m \times P_n, P_m \times C_n$ and $C_m \times C_n$

Let each vertex in $P_m \times P_n$ be represented by x_{ij} with i th row and j th column, where $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Therefore the results in this section goes with this notation in mind. We begin this section with the following lemma.

Lemma 2.1. *Given two paths P_m and P_n . Let $n \geq m \geq 2$ be positive integers with $m \not\equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then $\gamma_{ve}(P_m \times P_n) = (1 + \lceil \frac{n-5}{4} \rceil)(\lceil \frac{m-4}{4} \rceil + \lceil \frac{m-5}{4} \rceil + 2)$.*

Proof. Note that $P_m \times P_n$ has $2(n-1)(m-1)$ edges with 2 disjoint components H_1 and H_2 with equal number of edges i.e $E(H_1) = E(H_2) = (m-1)(n-1)$. Then we split the prove into the following two cases.

Case 1: For component H_1 .

Let $D_1 = \{x_{ij}, y_{ij}, z_{ij}, \dots\}$ be the vertex-edge dominating set of component H_1 in $P_m \times P_n$ such that for every $x_{ij}, y_{ij} \in D_1, d(x_{ij}, y_{ij}) \leq 4$ along both i th row and j th column. Fix the first vertex in D_1 to be the vertex x_{ij} where $i = j = 3$. Note that vertex x_{ij} can dominate edges up to when $i = j = 5$.

Next, we consider the edges when $i, j > 5$. Since $d(x_{ij}, y_{ij}) \leq 4$ for any arbitrary pair of consecutive vertices in D_1 along the i th row and j th column, we need $\lceil \frac{m-5}{4} \rceil \lceil \frac{n-5}{4} \rceil$ vertices to dominate the remaining edges for $i, j > 5$. Therefore the total number of vertices needed to vertex-edge dominate H_1 is $(x_{ij} + \lceil \frac{m-5}{4} \rceil)(x_{ij} + \lceil \frac{n-5}{4} \rceil)$ which gives $D_1 = (1 + \lceil \frac{m-5}{4} \rceil)(1 + \lceil \frac{n-5}{4} \rceil)$.

Case 2: For component H_2 .

Let $D_2 = \{u_{ij}, v_{ij}, w_{ij}, \dots\}$ be the vertex-edge dominating set of component H_2 in $P_m \times P_n$ such that for every $u_{ij}, v_{ij} \in D_2, d(u_{ij}, v_{ij}) \leq 4$ along both i th row and j th column. Fix the first vertex in D_2 to be vertex u_{ij} such that $i = 2$ and $j = 3$. In this case, vertex u_{ij} can dominate edges up to when $i = 4$ and $j = 5$.

Next, we consider the edges when $i > 4$ and $j > 5$. Note that for $i > 4(j > 5)$, we need $(\lceil \frac{m-4}{4} \rceil)(\lceil \frac{n-5}{4} \rceil)$ vertices to vertex-edge dominate H_2 along row (column) respectively since for every pair of vertices $u_{ij}, v_{ij} \in D_2, d(u_{ij}, v_{ij}) \leq 4$.

Therefore the total number of vertices needed to vertex-edge dominate H_2 is

$$D_2 = (i + \lceil \frac{m-4}{4} \rceil)(1 + \lceil \frac{n-5}{4} \rceil).$$

In conclusion, $\gamma_{ve}(P_m \times P_n) = \gamma_{ve}(H_1) + \gamma_{ve}(H_2) = D_1 + D_2$

$$= (1 + \lceil \frac{n-5}{4} \rceil)(\lceil \frac{m-4}{4} \rceil + \lceil \frac{m-5}{4} \rceil + 2).$$

□

The following result gives the vertex-edge domination number of $P_m \times P_n$ whenever $m \not\equiv 1 \pmod{5}$.

Lemma 2.2. *Given two Paths P_m and P_n . Let $n \geq m > 4$ be positive integers with $m \not\equiv 1 \pmod{5}$, then $\gamma_{ve}(P_m \times P_n) = (1 + \lceil \frac{n-5}{4} \rceil)(\lceil \frac{n-4}{4} \rceil + \lceil \frac{n-5}{4} \rceil + 2)$.*

Proof. We split the prove into the following two cases since $P_m \times P_n$ has two disjoint components H_1 and H_2 .

Case 1: For component H_1 .

The result in case 1 in Lemma 2.1 also hold for component H_1 .

Case 2: For component H_2 .

Let $D_2 = \{u_{ij}, v_{ij}, w_{ij}, \dots\}$ be the vertex-edge dominating set of component H_2 with $d(u_{ij}, v_{ij}) \leq 4$ for any pair of consecutive vertices along i th row and j th column. Fix the first vertex in D_2 to be vertex u_{ij} with $i = 3$ and $j = 2$. This implies that vertex u_{ij} can vertex-edge dominate edges up to when $i = 5$ and $j = 4$. Then consider the edges whenever $i > 5$ and $j > 4$. The remaining edges along the row (column) can be vertex-edge dominated by $\lceil \frac{m-5}{4} \rceil (\lceil \frac{n-4}{4} \rceil)$ respectively. The total number of vertices needed to vertex-edge dominate H_2 is

$$\begin{aligned} D_2 &= (1 + \lceil \frac{m-5}{4} \rceil)(1 + \lceil \frac{n-4}{4} \rceil). \text{ Hence } \gamma_{ve}(P_m \times P_n) = \gamma_{ve}(H_1) + \gamma_{ve}(H_2) = D_1 + D_2 \\ &= (1 + \lceil \frac{m-5}{4} \rceil)(\lceil \frac{n-4}{4} \rceil + \lceil \frac{n-5}{4} \rceil + 2) \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

Remark 2.1. $\gamma_{ve}(P_m \times P_n)$ can be obtained by Lemma 2.1 or Lemma 2.2 whenever $m = n$ and $m \cong 1 \pmod{20}$.

Corollary 2.1. Given two graphs P_m and C_n . Let $n \geq m \geq 2$ be positive integers with $m \not\cong 1 \pmod{4}$, then $\gamma_{ve}(P_m \times C_n) = (1 + \lceil \frac{m-4}{4} \rceil)(\lceil \frac{m-4}{4} \rceil + \lceil \frac{m-5}{4} \rceil + 2)$

Proof. View the graph $P_m \times C_n$ as the graph $P_m \times P_{n+1}$ and applying the result in Lemma 2.1 gives the result. \square

Corollary 2.2. Given two paths P_m and C_n . Let $n \geq m > 4$ be positive integers with $m \not\cong 1 \pmod{5}$, then $\gamma_{ve}(P_m \times C_n) = (1 + \lceil \frac{m-5}{4} \rceil)(\lceil \frac{n-3}{4} \rceil + \lceil \frac{n-4}{4} \rceil + 2)$.

Proof. View the graph $P_m \times C_n$ as the graph $P_m \times P_{n+1}$ and applying the result in Lemma 2.2 gives the result. \square

In view of the above corollary, we have the following remark.

Remark 2.2. View the graph $C_m \times P_n$ as $P_{m+1} \times P_n$. The result in Corollary 2.1 holds for $\gamma_{ve}(C_m \times P_n)$ by interchanging m and n whenever $m \not\cong 0 \pmod{5}$. Also, the result in Corollary 2.2 holds for $\gamma_{ve}(C_m \times P_n)$ by interchanging m and n whenever $m \not\cong 0 \pmod{4}$

Theorem 2.1. Given two cycles C_m and C_n . Let $n \geq m \geq 2$ be positive integers with $m \not\cong 0 \pmod{4}$, then $\gamma_{ve}(C_m \times C_n) = (1 + \lceil \frac{n-4}{4} \rceil)(\lceil \frac{m-3}{4} \rceil + \lceil \frac{m-4}{4} \rceil + 2)$

Proof. View the graph $C_m \times C_n$ as the graph $P_{m+1} \times P_{n+1}$ and apply Remark 2.2 gives the result. \square

Theorem 2.2. Given two cycles C_m and C_n . Let $n \geq m > 4$ be positive integers with $m \not\cong 0 \pmod{5}$, then $\gamma_{ve}(C_m \times C_n) = (1 + \lceil \frac{m-4}{4} \rceil)(\lceil \frac{n-4}{4} \rceil + \lceil \frac{n-3}{4} \rceil + 2)$.

Proof. View the graph $C_m \times C_n$ as the graph $P_{m+1} \times P_{n+1}$ and applying Remark 2.2 gives the desired result. \square

3. Vertex-edge domination of $P_m \times K_n, C_m \times K_n$ and $K_m \times K_n$

We begin with the following result.

Theorem 3.1. Let $n \geq 2$ be a positive integer, then $\gamma_{ve}(K_{n,n} - I) = 2$.

Proof. Let $D = 2$ be the vertex-edge dominating set of $K_{n,n} - I$. Let $x \in D$ be any arbitrary vertex in $K_{n,n} - I$. Then we split the proof into the following two cases.

Case 1: When $D < 2$.

Assume that $\gamma_{ve}(K_{n,n} - I) = D_1 = D - x$, this implies that $\gamma_{ve}(K_{n,n} - I)$ contains only one vertex, say y . Note that vertex y is adjacent to all the vertices at the other partite set except one vertex, say w . This implies that vertex w is not adjacent to any vertex in D_1 . Therefore D_1 cannot be the vertex-edge dominating set for $K_{n,n} - I$.

Case 2: When $D > 2$

Assume that $\gamma_{ve}(K_{n,n} - I) = D_2 = D + \{w\}$ where w is an arbitrary vertex in $K_{n,n} - I$. Note that each vertex in each partite set is adjacent to all the vertices in the other partite set except one vertex. Obviously, one vertex in each partite set can vertex-edge dominate $K_{n,n} - I$. Therefore, D_2 cannot be the minimum vertex-edge dominating set for $K_{n,n} - I$.

Hence the vertex-edge dominating set of $K_{n,n} - I$ is $D = 2$. □

Remark 3.1. $P_m \times K_n$ can be view as m partite sets with n vertices in each set.

Theorem 3.2. The vertex-edge dominating set $\gamma_{ve}(P_m \times K_n) = 2\lfloor \frac{m+2}{4} \rfloor$ for any positive integers $n \geq m \geq 2$.

Proof. Let D be the vertex-edge dominating set of path P_m . Then each vertex of P_m give rise to partite set with n vertices in $P_m \times K_n$. Also, each edge in path P_m give rise to $K_{n,n} - I$ in $P_m \times K_n$. This implies that we have $m - 1$ copies of $K_{n,n} - I$.

Applying Theorem 3.1 to D give the desired result since each vertex and edge in P_m give rise to partite set and $K_{n,n} - I$ respectively in $P_m \times K_n$. □

Corollary 3.1. For any positive integer $n \geq m \geq 2$, the $\gamma_{ve}(C_m \times K_n) = 2\lfloor \frac{m+3}{4} \rfloor$.

Proof. The number of edges in $C_m \times K_n$ is the same as the number of edges in $P_{m+1} \times K_n$. Therefore, applying Theorem 3.1 and Theorem 3.2 gives the result. □

Theorem 3.3. For any positive integer $n \geq m \geq 2$, the $\gamma_{ve}(K_m \times K_n) = 2$.

Proof. Each vertex in K_m give rise to partite set with n vertices in $K_m \times K_n$ and each edge in K_m give rise to $K_{n,n} - I$ in $K_m \times K_n$. Let $\gamma_{ve}(K_m) = D$, then applying Theorem 3.1 to D gives the result. That is, $2D = 2$ since $\gamma_{ve}(K_m) = 1$. Hence the result. □

In view of the results in Theorem 3.2, Corollary 3.1, and Theorem 3.3 we have the following result.

Theorem 3.4. Let G be a connected graph, then $\gamma_{ve}(G \times K_n) = 2\gamma_{ve}(G)$

We concluded with the following.

In general, for any connected graph G , $\gamma_{ve}(G) \leq \gamma_{ve}(G \times K_n) \leq 2\gamma_{ve}(G)$.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to thank the referees for the useful suggestions.

A. I did the experiment, gave the idea and A. D. interpreted the results and wrote the paper.

References

- [1] Boutrig R, Chellali M, Haynes TW and Hedetniemi ST. Vertex-edge domination in graphs. *Aequationes Mathematicae* 2016; 90: 355-366.
- [2] Chen X, Yin K and Gao T. A note on independent vertex-edge domination in graphs. *Discrete Optimization* 2017; 25: 1-5.
- [3] Haynes TW, Hedetniemi ST and Slater PJ. *Fundamentals of Domination in Graphs*, Monographs and Textbook in Pure and applied Mathematics, 208, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1998.
- [4] Klostermeyer WF. Dominating vertex covers: The vertex-edge domination problem. *Discussiones Mathematicae Graph theory* 2021; 41: 123-132.
- [5] Krishnakumari B, Venkatakrisnan YB and Krzywkowski M. Bounds on the vertex-edge domination number of a tree. *C.R. Math. Acad. Sci. Paris* 2014; 352: 363-366.
- [6] Krishnakumari B, Chellali M, Venkatakrisnan YB. Double vertex-edge domination. *Discrete Mathematics Algorithms and Application* 2017; 9.
- [7] Lewis J. vertex-edge and Edge-vertex parameters in graphs. (PhD Thesis, Clemson University, Clemson SC) Retrieved from <https://tigerprints.clemson.edu/alldissertations>.
- [8] Lewis J, Hedetniemi S, Haynes T and Fricke G. Vertex-edge domination. *Util.Math* 2010; 81: 193-213.
- [9] Peters J. Theoretical and Algorithmic results on Domination and Connectivity, PhD Thesis, Clemson University, 1986.
- [10] Shanmugavelan S and Natarajan C. An updated survey on distance-based domination parameters in graphs. *Asia Mathematica* 2020; 4: 134-149.
- [11] Siva Rama Raju SV. External vertex-edge domination. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics* 2019; 15: 981-995.
- [12] Ziemann R and Zylinski P. Vertex-edge domination in cubic graphs. *Discrete Mathematics* 2020; 343.
- [13] Zylinski P. Vertex-edge domination in graphs. *Aequationes Mathematicae* 2019; 93: 134-149.